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Ways to Organize a Marketing Service at a Furniture Manufacturing Enterprise and Increase its Effectiveness

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Abstract: *In this article, the essence and modern forms of the marketing concept in the production enterprise are researched, the current state of the furniture production industry and the activity of the marketing service are analyzed, the marketing activity is analyzed, its special aspects are revealed, and proposals are made for the formation of marketing services. output is considered.*

Keywords: *Enterprise, concept, service, activity, analysis, market, product, strategy.*

Introduction. In the third priority direction of the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates "... organization of entrepreneurial activities and sources of permanent income creating conditions for the formation, increasing the share of the private sector in the gross domestic product to 80% and its share in exports to 60%. Priority tasks such as "supporting entrepreneurship in the regions, improving the activities of existing structures for reducing unemployment and poverty" are also one of the guarantees for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Along with saturating the market of our country with goods, private entrepreneurship makes a great contribution to creating new jobs, earning additional income, and increasing the welfare of the people. As the President of our country Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "If the people are rich, the state will be rich and strong."¹.

A number of decrees and decisions of the President of our country are dedicated to the development and comprehensive support of entrepreneurship. Among them, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5718 dated May 14, 2019 "On measures to radically improve the system of support and protection of entrepreneurial activity" can be included. The important aspect of this Decree is that It has been emphasized that there are a number of negative factors preventing the wider and active involvement of the population in business activities, primarily related to the lack of a practical and transparent system of communication between state bodies and entrepreneurs, and it is important to eliminate this situation. The secret mechanism is defined.

Analysis of literature on the topic Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical

¹Sh. Mirziyoev. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of activity of every leader. - Tashkent.: "Uzbekistan". - 2017. - 102 p.

application. Among them, we can include famous scientists such as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the theory of marketing in the economy, while the researches conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years are based on national characteristics. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Parдав, R. Ibragimov. Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, R. Boltaboev, D. Ergashkhodjaeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Are to determine the ways of scientifically and methodologically justifying the introduction of the concept of marketing service development in furniture production enterprises.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined and fulfilled in the scientific article:

Researching the essence and modern forms of the marketing concept;

Researching the content of marketing services, the theory of their organization, their place and features in the economy;

Analysis of the current state of the furniture manufacturing industry and the activity of the marketing service;

Analyzing the marketing activity of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" limited liability company, revealing its special aspects;

To offer new approaches of marketing service in the field of furniture production;

Development of proposals for the formation of regional marketing services in the furniture industry based on the experience of our country and foreign companies.

At the same time, it should be mentioned that methodological work on the application of theoretical developments to practice and application in enterprises is insufficient. In order to implement the theoretical recommendations related to marketing relations, especially in furniture manufacturing industrial enterprises, it is necessary to draw from the experience and specifics of each field, conduct appropriate scientific research, and develop recommendations and systems for the introduction of the theory. In the development strategy of New Uzbekistan, the development of this sector is reflected in goal 22, i.e., to increase the production volume of industrial products by 1.4 times by continuing the industrial policy aimed at ensuring the stability of the national economy and increasing the share of industry in the gross domestic product. : Increasing the volume of production of "Furniture" products by 2.8 times".

If we look at the history of HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL limited liability company, it started its activity like many business entities from a small carpentry shop. From 1996 to today, it has grown into a large furniture manufacturing enterprise. In 2003, it was transformed into a limited liability company with this name, and in 2006, the large-scale production of various furniture for the population, enterprises, organizations and institutions was launched.

Table 1

Production indicators of HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL LLC in 2020-2023

No	Indicator name	Amount by years			
		2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Production volume, million soms	8745.7	9443.6	10402.1	11688.5
2	Annual growth rates of production, %	100	107.98	110.15	111.4
3	Change compared to 2018, %	100	107.98	118.93	132.5

According to the data, "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC is constantly increasing production volumes. 11 billion by 2023. Products worth 588 million soums were produced, which is 1.3 times more than in 2020. We can clearly observe the change of production volumes in the following diagrams.

Information on the range of products manufactured at HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL LLC is presented in the table below (Table 2).

Table 2

In 2020-2023, the range of products of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC, million soms.

No	Type of furniture	Annual production, million soms				Annual growth, %		
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2021	2022	2023
1	Kitchen furniture	1542.7	4089.4	2159.5	3387.3	265.1	52.8	156.6
2	Soft furniture	4693.8	3694.5	5570.3	4893.9	78.7	150.8	87.8
3	Office furniture	18.4	12.3	232.0	486.2	66.9	1888.9	209.6
4	Bedroom furniture	797.6	391.1	183.1	404.4	49.0	46.8	220.9
5	Wooden table and chairs	417.2	11.3	151.8	155.5	2.7	1339.8	102.3

6	Magazine tables	593.0	272.1	536.7	752.7	45.9	197.3	140.2
7	Mattress	683.0	975.8	1568.6	1608.3	142.9	160.7	102.5
	Total	8745.7	9443.6	10402.1	11688.5	107.98	110.15	111.4

As can be seen from the information presented in the table, there is an increase in the production of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC according to the main positions of the assortment. We can only see a decrease in the production of bed furniture and mattresses. In this case, the actions of competitors in the Samarkand furniture market for bed furniture can be cited as the reason. At the same time, as a result of the specialization of furniture production, it is necessary to emphasize the active service of other partner enterprises with mattress production. In 2020, we can see the high growth rates of the production of kitchen furniture and wooden tables and chairs in the activities of HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL LLC.

At the same time, it will be necessary to analyze the change in the composition of the assortment in order to draw conclusions about individual assortment positions. We will study the share of product types in the total production.

Table 3

The composition of the product range of HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL LLC in 2020-2023, %

No	Type of furniture	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Kitchen furniture	17.64	43.29	20.76	28.98
2	Soft furniture	53.67	39.11	53.55	41.87
3	Office furniture	0.21	0.13	2.23	4.16
4	Others	9,12	4.14	1.76	3.46
5	Wooden table and chairs	4.77	0.12	1.46	1.33
6	Magazine tables	6.78	2.88	5.16	6.44
7	Mattress	7.81	10.33	15.08	13.76
	Total	100	100	100	100

From the data in the table and pictures, we can see that in 2020, the main part of the assortment was made up of three types of products - soft furniture (24.24%), office furniture (32.32%) and bed furniture (28.28%). . The smallest place is occupied by kitchen furniture (0.61%). In 2022, we will see big changes in the composition of the assortment. Office furniture (29.63%) and soft furniture (24.69%) are in the leading positions. The share of bedroom furniture decreased sharply and made 12.35%. The contribution of kitchen furniture production increased from 0.61% to 9.88%. Similarly, the production of wooden tables and chairs increased from 8.08% to 19.75%. The share of magazine tables and mattresses, which occupy a small place in the range of manufactured products, has further decreased and by 2023 will be 2.47% and 1.23%, respectively.

It can be concluded that in the past three years there have been major changes in the furniture market and HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL LLC's position in the market is also changing. This, in turn, requires the development of the enterprise's marketing activities.

"HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC's marketing activities are similar to all furniture manufacturing enterprises in the region. In this case, market research, product policy organization, pricing and sales promotion schemes depend on the enterprise's own initiative and capabilities.

Table 4

Composition of the sales volume in "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC in 2023

t/r	The name of the points of sale of goods	Sales volume, pcs	Sales volume, million soums
1	Sale of furniture products through dealers	5284	7691.6
2	Spare parts for furniture	5965	1718.7
3	Individuals	201	640.8
4	Legal entities	2740	1644.7
	Total	14190	11695.8

According to the research results, marketing of furniture products is not implemented in a fully developed manner. That is, the application of marketing convenience and efficiency significantly develop the type of market the product being sold, competition in the market. It was found that it depends on age. To apply the marketing concept, it is important that there are no universal, standard, unified recommendations in marketing, everything in practical marketing depends on external and internal factors, demands significantly differs depending on consumer characteristics.

In Uzbekistan, 5-6 years ago, the "gross" approach prevailed in the application of the marketing concept, but at the same time, the differentiated approach is widely used. Manufactured furniture products, if we analyze them according to the types of content, 58 percent correspond to

household furniture, 39 percent to organizational furniture, and 3 percent to other furniture. A bit about thatpleaseLtd. makes office furniture and special furniture for educational institutions, shops, hospitals, restaurants, stores, warehouses, hairdressing salons, etc.

Manufacturer of furniture productsThe regional analysis of aging composition showed that the main part of the furniture produced in 2022 was sold to the city and region of Samarkand. The share of regions in sales was as follows: Tashkent cityto -377.1 million soums, to Fergana region - 94.8 million soums, to the city of Karshi679.3 million soums, to the city of Bukhara -103.0 million soums..

As noted above, the stable ri of any networkproduce only those goods that are in demand-directly related to growth and sales. And this, in turn, marketing activities of network enterprises saDeer organization, furnitureregular studyit requires taking into account the wishes of consumers, and analyzing the factors of the purchase process in detail. Technological change, the increasing role of social media, demographic changes, and the increasing purchasing power of women are all influencing the marketing efforts of furniture manufacturers and retailers.sobare the main points to be taken into account. We are our countryhistory in studying consumer preferences for waist products, macustommoms and furniture productsbased on their characteristics, we found it appropriate to segment them.

The establishment and operation of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC is closely related to "GULABAD MEBEL" LLC. First of all, both the founders of the studied object and "GULOBAD MEBEL" LLC, as well as the location, show the interdependence of the world. The emergence of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC is related to the wide segmentation of the furniture market and the increasing competition in it. Practice shows that the production of a wide range of products does not always give creative results. The difference in technologies leads to a sharp increase in production costs.

The main reason for specialization in furniture production is that the brand's product policy occupies a large place in the furniture market. Buyers associate a certain type of furniture with a particular brand, so it is necessary to abandon universality in order to select and maintain a target segment.

If we observe the activities of "HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC, since its establishment, soft furniture, kitchen furniture and mattresses occupy the main part of the assortment. Analysis shows that new modern "Luxury" and "Exclusive" category furniture is almost not found in the company's assortment. Most of the kitchen furniture is occupied by "Tashkent" furniture collection. Therefore, it can be concluded that these two furniture manufacturers are using certain differentiation strategies in terms of specialization.

When buying furniture products, consumers have a wide rangeuses the information in, that is: analyzes various information, tries to find the optimal purchase option, chooses the product based on his lifestyle, taste and opportunity. Also, the consumer takes into account financial, technical, time loss and psychological risks when purchasing a durable product.

The buyer performs the purchase and use of home appliances only after clarifying his need, which consists of several interrelated steps to make the purchase decision. That is, the general need-to solve the problems in recommended:

- what kind of furniture is his? It is clear that it will fully satisfy your needs;
- the goods from the market, the firm buys from a store or through the Internet;
- what are the advantages of the product, what kind of warranty does the seller provide, how long can this product be used?

How influential is the media for buying furniture? The analysis shows that 52.5 percent of the population read TV shows, 43.1 percent read advertisements in newspapers and magazines. Of those, 49.7 percent are company stores. 50.6% of visits to use catalogs and brochures.

Furniture manufacturers need to improve the positioning process in order to achieve a competitive advantage and ensure a stable place for their products in the target market and in the minds of consumers, clearly different from the products of competitors. Enterprises in this field direct their considerable efforts in the implementation of marketing activities to the formation of a marketing complex. As a result, there is a lag in the process of positioning, which plays an important role in the systematic and effective marketing activities of enterprises. When positioning the product, attention should be paid to developing the consciousness of customers and modernizing it.

Failure to properly organize the positioning process of furniture manufacturing enterprises can cause the following negative consequences:

- If the manufacturer does not determine the position of the product in the market, in this case the consumer can perform this task himself and the company may not be able to have the position it expects, and may even lead to the formation of a negative image;
- Marking of a position that is close to the position of a competitor's, without clearly indicating its unique characteristics, different from competitors' goods - can serve to have the opposite effect, rather than to motivate the consumer to buy the product;
- Failure to provide a clear position of the product may interfere with the formation of the marketing complex and ensure its sequence, and may even cause conflicting strategies for the formation of each element of the marketing complex.
- Even if the position is clearly chosen, however, if it is narrowly defined, such positioning can act as an obstacle to expanding the market of the existing goods of the enterprise and introducing new goods to the market. The main reason for this is the use of a common brand strategy in the industry.

Based on the above, furniture manufacturers should focus on two main areas in the positioning process:

- Determining the compatibility or, in other words, the matching point of the product being positioned. That is, on the basis of research, it is intended to determine which category of goods the company equates with in the minds of consumers, or rather, which category they include. This, in

turn, provides an opportunity to identify its direct competitors, based on the disclosure of the specific characteristics of the product category.

- Determining the point of differentiation of the product being positioned. It consists in showing the competitive advantage of the product on the basis of identifying one or more specific features that are clearly different from the products of competitors.

- Furniture manufacturing enterprises should take into account the following specific features of the network before positioning in the highlighted areas:

- The complexity of the product production process and the high impact of technology. The production of modern furniture requires complex technologies, which ultimately leads to an increase in the market price of goods.

- The length of the period of launching the production of a new type and model of furniture. The average period of time for launching the production of a new model of furniture by large furniture manufacturing enterprises is 7-15 months.

- High demand for product quality. Since furniture is a type of goods that require prior selection, consumers expect long-term service from the product. In order to maintain the quality of their products at a high level, industry manufacturers use high-quality fittings in their production, while maintaining its functional nature. Therefore, many companies use the words "quality", "solid" in positioning their products.

Warranty service. Usually, the cost of warranty service and post-warranty service is not high, but in some cases it can be 20-25% of the cost of the product. Also, after-sale furniture collection service can be equal to 10% of the cost of the product.

The consumer spends a lot of time on the product selection and purchase process. Marketing research shows that in the consumer goods market, a consumer can spend up to 4 weeks choosing and purchasing furniture.

The above problems and specifics of marketing activities in furniture production push forward the need to develop a strategic and tactical program for a separate marketing service for enterprises.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

As a way to speed up the economy in the "Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" developed at the request of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev..assimilation of new types of products and technologies in principle, ensuring the competitiveness of national goods in domestic and foreign markets on this basis; "Continuing the policy of promoting the localization of production and, first of all, replacing the import of consumer goods and components, expanding inter-sectoral industrial cooperation" have been defined. - 100 goals" strategy has been further strengthened.

These tasks require domestic enterprises to apply marketing principles in the conditions of modern market conditions, to develop international competitiveness. First of all, it is necessary to carefully study the forms and methods of marketing research, which are market tools. In this regard,

we have studied the theoretical and practical aspects of marketing services in health enterprises in the graduation work and came to the following main conclusions.

Marketing services are one of the main links of modern marketing activities and occupy one of the largest places in marketing theory. In marketing philosophy, organizational aspects of marketing services for enterprises are the basis for production decisions.

Marketing services are carried out in various forms and forms under the influence of the intended goals, market subjects, type of goods, market conditions, and many other factors. At the same time, marketing services are united by the same principles.

"HAVAS COMFORT FURNITURE LLC" is located in the Samarkand district of the Samarkand region and is mainly adapted to the production of various types of furniture. The company produces furniture for the domestic market and today has an assortment of about 50 types. The company employs 52 people.

Marketing activities are mainly carried out by customer service professionals. The sales department of the enterprise sells the manufactured products through dealers and stores.

"HAVAS COMFORT FURNITURE" LLC chooses two ways in its marketing activities: a) to determine the wishes of the customer and study to what extent they are fulfilled during the order fulfillment period. This method is mainly used for individual orders, that is, furniture that is selected in accordance with the rooms, and as a result, the mass catalog is also extended to furniture; b) Meeting the needs of potential consumers based on samples and catalogs available in the enterprise.

As a result of the conducted research, we developed the following proposals for the development of marketing research in the enterprise:

- expanding the forms and scope of marketing services, i.e. applying functional, product and matrix structures, etc., widely used in market relations;
- Implementation of the marketing outsourcing system in the marketing services system, i.e. implementation of marketing services with the help of external organizations;
- Organization and development of marketing service based on digitization technology;
- Extensive use of benchmarking information in marketing services, study of the results of others' experiments;

The effect of these offers is reflected not only in the volume of sales, but also in the reputation of the enterprise.

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